

Article

Casteism in Practice: Some Personal Reflections*

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Abstract

In this lecture, the author discussed caste on the basis of his personal, day to day experience. He also discusses the views of Gandhi, Ambedkar and Tagore on caste.

Key terms : Brahmin , bhadrlok, caste, , panchayat, proletariat , refugee, Introduction

In an earlier volume of my essays on *Post Colonial Democracy in India*, (Mukhopadhyay Apurba Kumar, 2014) I have made a humble attempt at exploring the ubiquity of the caste system in India in its

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structural and processual aspects. What follows is a different kind of exercise in grasping the values and sentiments involving both inter personal and inter group relationships in the everyday life of common men and women in India. It would be more in the nature of a personal encounter with the idioms and practices of caste. I was born in a refugee Brahmin family during the 1950s. My father, a devout Brahmin frequently called upon to worship multitude of Hindu deities in many familiar households, also had to take up the job of a semi-skilled labourer in a private factory for making both ends meet. I was therefore destined to carry three distinct and also mutually incompatible identity markers of a Brahmin, a refugee and a proletariat respectively. While the first one contributed to my social esteem viewed in the light of the conventional caste hierarchy, the other two were by no means dignifying at all even in the socio cultural ambience of West Bengal, arguably known for its cultural renaissance and a very high level of secular political consciousness throughout the last century.

As I grew up and joined the salaried class during the 1970s amidst so much of political radicalism, I was tempted to share along with people of my generation a false consciousness that casteism and communalism are forbidden on the soil of Bengal where only the class culture rules the roost. Much of the socio political and literary writings on or about Bengal and the Bengalis fortified such belief. There were some western scholars like Broomfield and Marcus Franda who would try to swim against the tide and highlight the dominance of the *Bhadrals* represented in the main by the three castes of the Brahmins, the Kayasthas and the Vaidyas respectively in the socio-cultural and political lives of West Bengal. On the All-India plane, the stranglehold of caste as a socio-politically decisive identity marker was both theoretically and empirically substantiated through the writings of Rajni Kothari and the Rudolphs, apart from the orthodox sociologists like

M.N. Srinivas and Andre Beteille who would point towards the enormous potentialities of traditional caste hierarchy to adjust itself with gradual unfolding of the institutions and practices of parliamentary democracy in India and thereby acquire a new lease of life in the process of modernization of her society, polity and culture. Unlike intellectuals with revolutionary pretensions, amongst whom I would include myself as well, they were at least honest enough to substantiate their conclusions with considerable amount of exploration of ground level empirical realities. Radical interpretation of caste as an idiom for class politics would refuse to buy the logic of such scholars as methodologically functionalist, an exercise in romanticizing India's age-old tradition, if not also projecting a static view of political life of the common men and women of the country, passing through agonies and excitements of so much of change and transformation of their living conditions under socio-economic compulsions. Incidentally, the 1970s were marked by militant peasant movements organized in different parts of India by several ultra leftist groups drawing inspiration from the experiences of revolutionary China and invoking the ideas of Mao-Zhe-Dong. These movements came to be known afterwards as Maoist movements throwing up a major challenge against the post colonial Indian state. No specific caste identity could be attributed to the participants and organizers of these movements excepting the fact that an overwhelming majority of them belonged to the scheduled castes and scheduled tribes. In terms of class origin, most of them belonged to the category of small peasants, share croppers and landless agricultural labourers. The instances of radical mobilization of the peasants were viewed by us as a process of gradual but an automatic and irreversible syndrome of fragmentation of the hold of caste in traditional rural hierarchy.

Experience as a researcher

As I began my forays in empirical research into the interiors of rural West Bengal in connection with the study of land reforms at both micro and macro levels and the working of Gram Panchayats, during the three decades from 1978 to 2008, a whole series of new realities started unfolding before me. Social life in rural West Bengal appeared no less caste ridden than it had been in other parts of the country. The plight of the so called untouchables and the Adivasis remained least affected by the secular wisdom of the renaissance or Marxism as professed and practiced by the Bengali *bhadraloks* through generations. Absolute illiteracy was found among tribal women in villages in the districts of Birbhum, Burdwan, Bankura and Purulia. Illiteracy and ill health were rampant amongst men and women belonging to Harijans, Adivasis and also the Muslim minorities inhabiting the vast rural space in radical Bengal. No serious efforts were made to reform their social life to liberate them from various kinds of superstitions. Consumption of country liquor by the male members remained a chronic problem in most of the tribal and untouchable families. Their womenfolk often took the initiative to demolish the illicit country liquor shops inviting law and order problems in some remote corners of the state. They were made to reside in hamlets at a distance from the rural space occupied by the upper caste Bengali *bhadraloks*. One would therefore come across *Bagdipara, Bauripara, Muchipara, Santal Palli, Dhangar Para* and the like as identifiers of castes and tribes to which they belong. The high-low binary remained as formidable as ever in inter caste relationships, be it in the sphere of marriage or dining, no matter how progressive the outlook of the dominant upper caste Bengalis might be. Even after more than three decades of democratically elected Panchayats taking over political control of rural West Bengal, the socio cultural scenario would remain unchanged. The untouchables would be allowed to participate in ritual or social ceremonies in villages but without breaking the barriers of high and low

castes in those. In fact, any instance of marriage between a high caste woman and a low caste man would immediately create much consternation inviting violent reprisal from the members of the upper castes occupying the centre stage of the village. One could even notice instances of honour killing in such situations forced by *salisi sabhas* (the Kangaroo Courts) or the *Khap Panchayats*. A series of Ethnographic studies confirmed that there was hardly any indication of rural Bengal being exceptional in so far as values and sentiments of caste were concerned. The intensification of class solidarity and class based political mobilization failed to eradicate caste prejudice and even caste violence. A journey from Bengal to the north or to the south would bring out striking similarities between the casteist ways of life in different parts of rural India even after more than six decades of secularization of the social and political life of the country. This was a vindication of the contention of B.R. Ambedkar in his rather subversive text entitled 'Annihilation of Caste' way back in 1936 (Ambedkar, 2007) which had caused much heart burning for Mahatma Gandhi and other Hindu upper caste leaders of the freedom movement. Ambedkar saw little prospect of a reformed Hinduism sans caste and hence advised his untouchable caste followers to strive for an autonomous space to be carved out for themselves by way of organizing their own movements under their own leadership, snapping all ties with the orthodox Hindus. A symbolic advance towards this end was made by none other than Ambedkar himself when he embraced Buddhism with ten thousand members from the Mahar community to which he belonged, immediately preceding his death in 1956.

Ambedkar and Gandhi

In fact, Ambedkar and Gandhi approached the problem of untouchability from two diametrically opposite ends. While Ambedkar wanted the issue to be directly addressed by the victims of untouchability themselves through assertion of their autonomy from the Hindu system of Varna hierarchy altogether and the generation of a fresh batch of leadership from the depressed classes, Gandhi with his political acumen would seek to deliver the depressed classes from the ignominy and humiliation inflicted on them by the Hindu upper castes through a rigorous battle against the upper caste elites of which he himself happened to be a member. He would therefore, unlike Ambedkar, make the perpetrators, and not the victims, his addressee in championing the cause of abolition of the practice of untouchability. Ambedkar failed to appreciate the fact that by creating a small stratum of lower caste elites, he would open up the possibility of their getting isolated from the rank and file of their own community people on the one hand, and being gradually absorbed or co-opted in the ranks of the upper caste Hindu elites on the other. Gandhi hinted at such a possibility through an apparent dig at the development of the intellectual and political career of Ambedkar himself, receiving patronage from a Hindu potentate, in one of his rejoinders to Ambedkar's critique of his defense of the Varnashram Dharma in the pages of *Harijan*.

Gandhi could perhaps anticipate the rise of a creamy layer amongst the backward communities in course of implementation of the policy of reservation which was considered to be the cure all for the maladies of untouchability. More than six decades after Independence, the rise of this creamy layer has become a major bone of contention in inter caste relationships affecting society and politics in India. The policy of reservation meant for amelioration of socio cultural lives of backward communities in India, and, the practice of secularization of political culture in post colonial democracy have passed each other by over the

years. The instances of casteism in practice can be readily gleaned from the matrimonial columns of most of the newspapers which often take pains to single out caste-no-bar advertisements. In none of these does one come across any proposal of marriage between spouses representing the top and the bottom rungs of the caste hierarchy. Far from given any publicity, any such marriage if it takes place at all has to be negotiated and arranged in the most clandestine manner. This is no less true of our urban social culture than its rural counter parts. Most of the lower castes associated with menial jobs are still regarded as polluting by touch if not also by sight in some extreme cases. Gandhi was quite frank in his admission of the fact that he could not convince even his wife and many of his near and dear ones to overcome such a mind set in the Ashrams he had set up with people drawn from the highest and the lowest in the caste hierarchy of the Hindus. He failed, in other words, to secularize even his Ashrams at a time when he had launched a crusade against untouchability on a nationwide scale with a firm determination to reduce all members of his Ashrams to the rank of the *Bhangis*, that is, the scavengers. It is an irony of socio cultural practices in India that the metaphor of scavengers keeps haunting the nation's leaders from Mahatma Gandhi to Narendra Modi with little material imports accruing to the real scavengers of the country.

Politically speaking, the battle for castes has been the order of the day while the battle against castes has either not been contemplated with any sense of urgency or has been lost no sooner than it had been waged by some diehard anti-caste ideologues representing the genres of the Gandhians or the Marxists. In fact, a genuine anti-caste ideological orientation could be discerned in the tradition of the *Bhakti* movements organized by some minor sects amongst the Hindus, throwing up a few saintly men and women as their spiritual mentors, much before the intervention of the colonial state in India with its elaborate mechanisms

of counting and segregating groups of men and women exclusively in caste terms. Nanak, Kabeer, Sri Chaitanya dev and Meerabai are some of the names that readily come to mind. The small sects they represented, were relatively untrammelled by caste bindings and caste prejudices. But, their hold was restricted to micro levels of the vast societal space of India, and the messages they sought to impart, would fail to travel far and wide beyond a certain point of time. Worse, many of these sects would begin to take on an exclusivist orientation of their own, specifying rituals and practices that would mark them off from others and confer on them a separate identity in a pluri-cultural society already carrying the burden of so many identities.

Caste & colonialism

The advent of colonialism dispelled the fuzziness of identities instead of displacing those. The process of identification of groups of people in caste terms and their enumeration through the operation of the decennial census, part of the colonial governmentality, added to the life span of caste structures and caste sentiments in colonial India. Freedom fighters of diverse ideological hues would fail miserably to replace the idiom of caste by a more secular class or national idiom although their overtures would remain firmly nationalist and anti-racist to give it the appearance of a secular, anti-colonial movement. The principle of inequality, embedded in caste hierarchy, would engender a high-low divide amongst socio-cultural groups marked by umpteen differences in their ways of life. Hierarchy and difference would mutually reinforce each other and breed contempt and exclusion in inter-group relationships. The nationalist elites would at the most adopt an attitude of patronage vis-a- vis the lowly placed ones. An outright

rejection of the caste system, an inextricable part of the Hindu *Varnashram Dharma*, would be considered too radical a mission by the votaries of orthodox Hinduism dominating the movement for nationalist awakening in colonial India. A cosmetic surgery in place of total transplantation of the system of caste hierarchy was recommended by a majority of the Hindu leadership of the national movement through granting of a whole series of social, economic and political concessions to those occupying the bottom rungs of the Hindu social hierarchy. There were movements for recognition of the right to enter temples of the Hindus by the untouchables, polluting castes organized with much fanfare by sections of the upper caste Hindu elites. Gandhi was deeply concerned about the inhuman practice of untouchability and he pledged its abolition as an integral part of the movement for national liberation. But he had to face stiff resistance from two diametrically opposed directions. His upper caste followers were least prepared to remove caste barriers in the private domain of their lives and least willing to give up their fidelity to the sacred-profane binary in everyday life. His untouchable followers on the other hand, were increasingly sensitized to the discriminatory treatments meted out to them overtly in the private domain of interpersonal lives and covertly in the public sphere, notwithstanding the Mahatma's sermons and hence unprepared to take his anti-untouchability campaign with an iota of seriousness. Such frivolity in the conceptualization of an anti-caste battle by both the sides provided the rhyme and reason for the sustenance of the symbols and practices of casteism in India during the post-colonial period when India was supposed to march ahead as a strong and vibrant democracy delivering all goods to all men and women also, perhaps. Interestingly enough, the deepening of democratic processes in India contributed immensely towards forging a strong dalit identity, even cutting across religious divides. Far from the Hindus being put on

the dock, we now have Dalits amongst the Muslims and the Christians as well. Dalit identity has now emerged as a secular formation proclaiming the existence of its own literary and cultural traditions if not also its own messiahs. Ambedkar has been regarded as the chief spokesman of Dalit cause. The Scheduled Caste Federation founded by him before independence was renamed as the Republican Party of India that would take part in electoral politics with an exclusive Dalit agenda in different parts of the country. Of late, there has been a flurry of dalit literature claiming separate origin in the writings of men and women belonging to their own caste. The Indian state has, from time to time, conceded more and more socio economic and political grounds to them through the device of reservation and caused increasing upper caste heart burning in the process. As a result, movements for and not against caste have become the norm in the process of unfolding of India's post colonial democracy.

Caste in Post-colonial India

I, therefore, continue to retain my identity as a Brahmin, despite refusing to wear the sacred thread. There is little possibility of the Dalits taking my anti caste if not also anti Hindu postures with any amount of seriousness; nor am I in a position to critically interrogate the status of the dalits as dalits irrespective of their social class position. I have rather the unenviable position of being rejected by both the Dalits and the Brahmins as an outcaste and also an outsider to the socio cultural main stream of the Indian society. Perhaps the situation would have been much better had there been more such outsiders to the so called main stream so as to debunk the same. There was a time when the Dalits would strive for upward mobility along the lines of

Hindu caste hierarchy through adoption of symbols and rituals of the Brahmins, a process rightly designated by M.N. Srinivas as 'Sanskritization'. The nationalist leadership used this tendency as a ploy to co-opt the Dalits within the fold of Hindu caste hierarchy. Post colonial democratic policies and practices replaced Brahminical supremacy by the authority of the numerically dominant caste as available in various regions. The voice of the Dalits remained unheard in either of these symbolic gestures. They had only the benefits of reservation to make amends for their socio cultural ignominies. Quite naturally they were made to demand more and more of such benefits causing a sharp increase in caste based polarization. Caste, like religion has therefore become an unavoidable identity marker in India since independence giving increasing credibility to the dalit voice for autonomy and exclusiveness. Their claim has been fortified by the inclusion of members of other religions into their ranks. The process of politicization of the dalits which took off from the symbolic practice of Sanskritization from the late medieval period down to independence has by now turned a full circle giving rise to what many commentators on Indian politics describe as the process of Dalitization of politics. It has assumed a secular form by mixing up various religious communities within its fold while interestingly stalling the process of secularization of caste itself through its annihilation, as proposed by Ambedkar long back. In its newly fortified group identity, Dalits are no less active in West Bengal and Kerala, Marxist strong holds, than in the remaining parts of the country where the class idiom hardly exists. Under the new circumstances, Marxist radicalism has been forced to take both theoretical and empirical cognizance of caste and workout its political strategies and tactics accordingly. New forms of social movements centering round economic demands of poor peasants, agricultural labourers and workers belonging to the unorganized sectors and cultural demands of the lower castes and Dalits

are now being contemplated by the practitioners of left politics in India as the twin maladies calling for their attention. The complex nature of such intertwining of social identities gives rise to what some Marxist commentators would describe as an interpenetration between caste and class. Class based political mobilization, notwithstanding its secular credentials, has failed to attract the attention of the common people of India, particularly in terms of its bearing on electoral democracy. In various regions of the country, caste based political organizations appearing in the shape of regional political parties could earn quick electoral dividends as can be seen from the electoral outcomes in both parliamentary and assembly elections. Parties making a secular projection of their ideological and organizational makeup and keeping a safe distance from an exclusively casteist or religious identity would cut a relatively sorry figure at the hustings. This has led some political pundits to claim that politics in India is primarily fought over issues of caste and community. Such claims have gained further credibility during the last three decades of democratic political churning in India consequent upon the arrival of the era of coalitions. Regional political parties with decisive inclinations towards specific castes and communities have emerged as major stakeholders in the process of competitive political mobilization so much so that their combined strength equals, if not outweighs, the support base of the two dominant all India parties like the Indian National Congress and the Bharatiya Janata Party. When this aspect of political realities in post colonial India is grafted on to the other aspect of class based polarization between the extremely rich and the moderately rich on one hand and the poor and the very poor on the other, class politics becomes fuzzy and incongruent with the composition of democratically elected bodies overtly unwilling to demobilize caste as an identity marker.

Multiple and fragmented identities

As I began this essay with a self description showing several identities that I had been forced to

Carry as a burden of my birth, I would come back to the complex ways in which multiple and fragmented identities accompany an ordinary Indian. My objective here is to show that such identities are not necessarily compatible with one another and also that these are not separable from one another either, almost through the entire life span of an individual. A poor Brahmin is as easily identifiable with his rich counterpart as a poor Dalit with a rich one. The rich-poor binary is easily fragmented by the identity of caste in such instances. It is here that one comes across the funny interplay between hierarchy and difference. With the passage of time, the elements of difference have over shadowed those of hierarchy, thanks to implementation of the policy of protective discrimination by the welfare state that India had turned out to be in its post-colonial avatar. The rich-poor divide embedded in caste hierarchy may be easily translated into the idiom of class as Ambedkar was so fond of propagating at the beginning of his intellectual and also political career. As a seasoned politician during the fag end of India's freedom movement when he would be called upon to draft the Constitution of the forthcoming Indian Republic, he would gradually shift his focus away from the class based hierarchy to that of differential social status expressed through the idiom of caste, happily reconciled to the policy of enumeration of communities based on distinctive identity markers and calling for differential share in the crumbs offered by the State to each of such specific communities. What is overlooked in the process would be the multiple points of overlap and intersections amongst such communities.

A new line of research work initiated at the behest of the Anthropological Survey of India as late

as 1985 would throw fresh light in this direction, presenting a more complicated caste-class scenario than had hitherto been explored. This study, running into as many as 43 volumes identifies 4635 discrete communities merrily overlapping each other and questioning the very rationale for understanding society and culture in India exclusively in caste or community terms. For politicians, however, the compulsions of vote bank politics in a competitive multi party system would require mobilization of groups along such lines, notwithstanding the lack of either conceptual or empirical validity of such markers. The only silver lining in such a cultural ambience is the plurality and fragmentation of such identities often working at cross purposes. One would therefore come across a Brahmin Jute Mill worker harping on his working class identity as long as his factory remains open and switching over to his Brahminical Identity to take up the priestly occupation as and when the mill is closed. The material condition of such a person calls for retention of both his identities up his sleeve. Dalit identity is similarly retained as a matter of convenience by a person for his or her descendants for gaining an easy access to educational or job opportunities in times of crisis although the person concerned might not be considered at par with his or her fellow members placed at the bottom rungs of the class hierarchy. It is the usefulness of such cross cutting identities that provides a permanent lease of life to the plurality of identities that an average Indian is born with. Caste practices and caste sentiments are therefore deeply embedded in *Varnashrama Dharma* of the Hindus. Its appropriation by the discourse of modernity with its secular, rational and utilitarian values is confirmed by the fact that followers of other religions like Islam, Christianity and Sikhism also do not find anything wrong in flaunting caste identity although in terms of origin, they have nothing to do with it. Indeed, Islam was founded on the principle of intrinsic equality among human beings. And Sikhism

basically emerged as a movement of protest against the caste based orthodoxy of Hinduism. The followers of both these religions embraced caste for its heuristic value as we have discussed above. For us it is better to look into the present history of India rather than its past for the ubiquity of the caste system of the Hindus.

Concluding Remarks

In its traditional version, the caste system as an inextricable part of the Hindu *Dharma Shastras* represented a functional division among the Hindus preordained by birth with little scope for transgressing borders laid down amongst the *Varnas* with specific prescriptions of rituals and codes to be followed by each. While implying some sort of a ritual hierarchy not ordinarily changeable, the caste system also prescribed certain rights and duties assigned to each. Those who were placed at the bottom of the ritual pyramid enjoyed certain safe guards against socio economic adversities and uninhibited repression from the higher varnas, and also legal protection against violation of their bodies and well being, howsoever small and intangible such benefits might turn out to be. Within the overarching Hindu religious norms and values, each of them would enjoy a certain modicum of autonomy. Secondly, caste as Varna being an exclusively religious identity, the state as the embodiment of legal and political authority had little role to play in shaping relationships within and between members of the distinctively identifiable castes. The pre-colonial Indian state in its many avatars remained an exterior part of the society, scratching only the surface of the later, without ever being deeply involved in the quotidian life of the people. The approach to situate caste as purely occupational categories arranged in both horizontal

and vertical order accompanied by the notion of purity and pollution emerged as an afterthought in a relatively modern period, prompted by the intrusion of too many religions and cultures into the erstwhile Hindu way of life. The exposure of the lower varnas to such new ways of life sensitized them to the possibility of bringing about a change in their life situations for the better either through religious conversions or through formation of discrete sects within the fold of Hinduism or beyond it. Over the last two centuries, caste, therefore, hardly remained an inseparable part of Hindu orthodoxy by metamorphosing itself into a whole range of identity groups cutting across religious divides and taking on political positions directly addressed to the state, colonial, and, post-colonial since 1947. Each of them would be identified by an occupation, a set of rules relating to matrimonial relations and a certain conception of purity and pollution shared by the members of the in-group, marking off one such group from the others. With the passage of time even the hierarchy based on purity and pollution would become highly flexible with the Brahmins losing their pan Indian supremacy. A Bengali, meat eating Brahmin like me would be subjected to all sorts of ridicule in the comity of Brahmins in both northern and southern India. The Jats in UP would refuse to take water from the hands of the Brahmins. Under the new ambience, even the Dalits would begin to assert their autonomy in terms of literary and cultural resources having nothing in common with the original Hindu mythologies and scriptures. In a sense, therefore, the process of secularization of caste began at popular levels as part of a long historical transformation without the Hindu elite's faint acknowledgement of the same. There was a gap between the Hindu upper caste elites' attempts at social reforms for amelioration of the existential conditions of those lying below and the Dalits' own initiative towards secularizing and modernizing their life situations through reforms of prevailing customs and socio cultural practices from

within, alongside protracted battles against socio cultural and political dominations imposed from above by the members of the upper caste Hindus. It is unfortunate that scholars and academicians like us had to wait till the arrival of a Phule, Gandhi or an Ambedkar to become conscious of such a churning process which had a life span stretching far back into the history of ancient, medieval and early modern period. Much of the contemporary discourses on the caste system in general and the dalits in particular had their beginning in the borrowed wisdom from the west which would view caste only in the light of racism which would be part and parcel of their own cultural heritage. As the west could think only in terms of mitigating the harshness of racial hatred through the intervention of the legal armoury of the state in a modern world, it would impress upon social reformers and nationalist politicians in colonial and post independence India the need for suitable legislative measures to bring about a secularized and sanitized version of the caste system in India. Such discourses failed to take cognizance of the under currents of change in caste practices and caste sentiments taking place through ages and turning both the ideologies of hierarchy and autonomy upside down, thanks to an uninterrupted process of both horizontal and vertical mobilization of discrete caste groups.

In the light of the above discussion, one may feel tempted to rewrite the present history of caste in India. The temptation grows further as one views with awe the tendency on the part of the present rulers of the country to refashion India into a Hindu state, raking up partial memories of her past. That there were other religious communities in this historical past of India without having any fidelity to the Institutions and ideology of caste based inequality are happily glossed over. It is also not taking into consideration as to how such communities with or without the bonding of caste could manage to live together away from the

protective patronage of a pre colonial and pre modern state. Why should it become imperative for such communities now to look up to the state for ensuring their harmonious existence under the new dispensation? And how could the colonial or the post colonial state become an instrument for equalizing the unequal relationships persisting through ages? Two answers to these questions have been tentatively put across by protagonists of the colonial-post colonial state. One is the deepening of the legal Institutional framework of democracy viewed in western liberal terms. The other is rapid Industrialization of a predominantly rural- agrarian economy acting as a stagnant pool for all sorts of bigotry and superstitions accompanying the Institutions and practices of casteism. Interestingly enough, both these options conspicuous by their absence under colonial rule were sought to be pursued with unabated zeal by the planners and policy makers of post colonial democracy in India. One notices a remarkable similarity in the approaches of both Nehru and Ambedkar in this respect, drawn far away from the perspective of Gram-Swaraj so enthusiastically championed by Gandhi. In fact, Gandhi had a deep sense of history in underlining the trajectories of development of rural Indian society and hence, he could not altogether deprecate the unfolding socio-economic and cultural make-up of such a society. Colonial wisdom as it moulded the mindset of nationalist modernizers like Nehru and Ambedkar, tended to de-historicize the institutions and practices of caste in course of intensely politicizing the same and happily anticipating the safe burial of the caste system in an imagined Indian society, industrially advanced and democratically restructured, with the benefit of the wisdom of western modernity. Gandhian ideology by contrast, would be considered retrogressive and an anathema to the strategy of large-scale industrialization and urbanization contemplated by the planners of state-directed development in post-independence India. Gandhi

talked in vain about the grassroots initiative for development of the rural economy through the mediation of village Panchayats which had existed in popular imagination through pre-colonial ages. To delink the citizens of modern India from their historical ethos and put them in an ahistorical space of developmental imaginaries through intense politicization by the post-colonial state led to the unhappy consequences of an unending agony of battles for petty loaves and fishes to be dished out by an all pervasive state inviting only troubles to itself and running short of ideas to overcome those. The state could negotiate the onrush of so many demands for remedying prevailing inequalities in the distribution of wealth and resources for so many discrete social groups either through democratic decentralization of its delivery mechanism or through consolidation of an authoritarian regime suppressing too many recalcitrant voices. The Gandhian option for decentralization with some necessary correctives in tune with the exigencies of the new situation could have been a long term solution whereas the authoritarian option tried out by the Indian state from time to time would only complicate the task of the developmental state further. This was amply evident from the historical experiences of the post-independence state in India. The Panchayats finally got the mandate of *The Constitution of India* in the early 1990s not so much by way of revival of the sense of history for the power that be as it was at the behest of foreign lending agencies refusing to negotiate with an overarching state amidst the winds of a free market economy. Democratization now came in package with liberalization under the dispensation of neo-colonialism, as the idea of the centralizing state had earlier taken shape under the tutelage of colonialism. For the victims of inequality and social discrimination, it was a back to square one situation with little symptoms of an independent thinking that had some flashes at least in the thought processes of a Gandhi or a Tagore who could by no stretch of

imagination be dubbed as archaic or retrogressive. Both Tagore and Gandhi were extremely critical of inegalitarian and discriminatory practices of caste, and they unequivocally and squarely denounced the inbuilt mechanisms of repression underlying the caste system and invoked the spirit of an indigenous culture of resistance against the same, to be articulated at the level of popular consciousness by the masses themselves. The raw materials of this new articulation of popular mindset were available in traditional India's syncretic culture drawing inspiration from the religious systems of Buddhism and Jainism and the messages imparted by the Bhakti cult spread across diverse Indian religions. Tagore learnt the lessons of his religion of man from the songs of the Bauls and Fakirs who would be deconstructing the ideology of caste with the help of very simple language intelligible to the most ordinary men and women of society. Baul and Sufi songs were more effective as antidotes to the caste system than state sponsored policies and programmes for dismantling the social hierarchy embodied in the same. The nationalist and post-colonial leadership in India failed to interrogate caste with indigenous cultural resources available in India's multiple little traditions in their quest for a great homogenizing tradition which incidentally was non-existent. It is the colonial and post-colonial mythology that accompanied the social reconstruction of caste in its present avatar, wishing away the material and spiritual upbringing of the institutions and practices of the caste system and also the historically evolving modes of denial and resistance to the socio-cultural evils engendered by the same, through ages. The battle for a casteless society in modern India has, therefore, to begin along the trajectories of her socio-cultural history, rather than on the social canvas, drawn up by colonial, cultural anthropology with all its inbuilt symptoms of de-historicization.

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